

THE ROLE OF CREATIVE AND STYLISTIC SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN'S SCULPTURE. HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: This article describes in detail the role, history and development of creative-stylistic schools in Uzbekistan's sculpture, the relief type of sculpture in Uzbekistan at the beginning of the 20th century, and the traditions of realistic style in Uzbekistan's sculpture.

Keywords: sculpture, relief type, realistic style, basis of art pedagogy, art education.

Introduction:

In Uzbekistan, at the beginning of the 20th century, the relief type of sculpture began to emerge slowly. In 1918, with the opening of an art school in the country, all areas of fine art improved. Also, sculpting began to take off gradually. The training of young sculptors in art technical schools was not at a high enough level. For a long time there was a shortage of skilled sculptors. The park-alley and decorative sculpture are also not well formed.

Literature analysis and methodology:

The opinion that "although several sculptors created in Uzbekistan from the first half of the 20th century, a serious school had not yet been formed" is evidence of this. Information about the sculptures made in these years was vague and sparse. The catalogs of exhibitions preserved from that period do not show examples of sculpture, and the few photographs published in newspapers do not give a clear idea of the mentioned works.

Since the 1960s, the traditions of the realistic style in the sculpture of Uzbekistan have become more and more perfect, and the form and artistic level of the artistic image has shifted to a positive quality side. The increase in the number of experienced specialists created the main creative foundation for the development of the industry. This foundation, based on a strong scholastic foundation, has placed it high in its emergence as a serious art.

Since the main goal of majestic sculpture is to express advanced ideas, portray the image of national heroes and statesmen in exemplary form, this field develops parallel to the development of society and reflects the spirit of the times. In this sense, it is possible to observe and analyze the sculpture of Uzbekistan, which has developed during the last century and now takes a

worthy place in the treasure of our national art, in two periods. First: the period until the 1990s - the entry of sculpture into Uzbekistan and its creative formation; Second: The period of independence is to strengthen the national creative school of sculpture.

Results:

Although there are images of the national theme among the monuments erected in the 19th century, their plastic solution was weak in expressing typical features or in-depth interpretation. If we pay attention to the formation of sculpture in Uzbekistan, this process corresponds to the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. For example, at the beginning of the 20th century, many Russian artists came to Uzbekistan, they were involved in the development of visual arts and artistic education in the country.

The initial art education was conducted in the studios of artists' workshops, in the 1920s an art school was opened in Samarkand, and later in Tashkent. In these educational institutions, Uzbek artists and sculptors learned the secrets of fine art. The purpose of teaching visual arts is to develop observational skills in children, to be able to see things, and also to develop memory. It is known that more than 90% of the information received from the surroundings is received through the eyes, and the remaining 10% is absorbed through the ears, nose, mouth and other organs. These qualities are of particular importance in the training of the perception of existence, as well as in the training of the fundamentals of art history.

Discussion:

The usefulness of teaching fine arts in all general education schools was developed by the great Czech pedagogue Y. A. Komensky in his work "Great Didactics". Currently, one of the tasks of general education schools is to direct students to various professions and trades. In a number of regions, cities, and districts of our republic, special art and music schools for teaching visual arts to young people have been opened.

In such conditions, the formation and existence of a unique art school in Uzbekistan, which covers a wide range of students and followers, is of particular importance. The problems of professional training of specialists in the rapidly changing market of design services impose a special responsibility on researchers and scientists studying the current period of local design, because the successful promotion of Uzbek design in the domestic and global market of professional services largely depends on it.

In 1997, by the decree of the first President of our Republic, the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan was established, and with the same decree, the National Institute of Painting and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod was established. It was founded in 1954 on the basis of the Faculty of Fine Arts opened under the Tashkent Theater and Art Institute. The famous artists of Uzbekistan R. Ahmedov and O. Tatevosyan initiated the creation of higher art education. These professors, who created the foundations of artistic pedagogy, prepared a galaxy of teachers of the next generation, whose teaching methodology is primarily based on their rich design practice and is directly related to the methodological achievements of the best art and sculpture schools in the world.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that sculpture in our country was formed in the last century under the ideological shell of the former regime. No matter how creatively the professional skill and creative experience were mastered in the created works, they consisted of the image of "heroes" who are foreign and untouchable to our national space. For this reason, despite the fact that many statues were installed in our country until the 1990s, the impact on the development of the national school was not felt.

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